

Meleleuca Wellness Company

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Introduction

Melaleuca, is a personal care, cosmetic and nutritional products company founded in 1985 and it's headquarter is located in Idaho Falls, Idaho, USA. Melaleuca is considered as one of fastest-growing companies among 500 companies in early 90s however, it is now one of the largest privately owned companies in Idaho. Melaleuca now employ more than 2,500 employees and have their offices in Australia, Japan, New Zealand, Taiwan, Hong Kong, and United Kingdom. Melaleuca began sales in Jamaica, Singapore, and Netherlands.

Discussion

While at first built transcendently in light of melaleuca plant concentrates, the product line has since extended past this introductory centering. Melaleuca now showcases in excess of 300 things, for example, family unit cleaners, individual consideration things, pharmaceuticals and dietary supplements. The organization markets itself as being earth-accommodating, and a considerable lot of their products are affirmed natural. Melaleuca has been candid against the misuses inalienable to multi-level marketing and the harm they can bring about. By complexity, Melaleuca does not permit stock stacking (a practice utilized by numerous multi-level marketing organizations swaying them to buy up to a huge number of dollars worth of stock), confines the marketing tie to 7 eras, and precludes "breakaways" (an alternate practice generally found in multi-level marketing).

SWOT Analysis

Strengths

The beauty and grooming industry has very high fragmentation in terms of suppliers. These suppliers are local as well as global. Some of the prestige fragrances under the Melaleuca umbrella are areas where the suppliers of Melaleuca have lower power in that it is not the fragrance but the brand and the brand value that is associated with the brand that makes the product what it is today (Swayne, Duncan, & Ginter, 2012).

Though there are many suppliers in the market and a few of them are much bigger than the rest. However, over the years Melaleuca itself has become such a big brand that being associated with Melaleuca as a supplier is a prestige for them. Their credibility increases from becoming a Melaleuca supplier. Hence, Melaleuca has more power over them. In addition, the cost of switching the supplier for Melaleuca is very low. This also decreases the supplier power (Kongstvedt, 2012).

Melaleuca is not pressurized by the customer to adjust the pricing as per their demands. The sales promotion is the only time the customers get a discount on Melaleuca products. The number of customers is very large but the size of the individual order is so low that they cannot dictate to Melaleuca. However, since the switching cost is very low, the company has to remain on the edge all the time to be able to meet and exceed the customer expectations.

Challenges

The competitive rivalry in the industry is very high. For instance, if we only look at the anti ageing category we can see that there are so many brands and each has a very good standing in the market. Beauty products are all fighting to get their share in the market. Melaleuca is one of the fiercest competitors in the personal care category. Similarly, the

whitening and lightening products category is flooded with brands that vow to work the same wonders for the end consumers. It is very difficult to create unique selling proposition (Friesner, 2011). In addition, the technology and the science that goes in the making of the products are beyond the understanding of the laymen consumer. All customers want are the results.

Threat

The threat of substitutes differs with the product category. This is very high for some categories and very low for the others. For instance, when it comes to brands, the threat of substitute is very high. A consumer may use one shampoo today and look at a new variant advertisement and switch to another brand the very next time he goes for shopping. However, when it comes to perfumes, a person may not try one perfume one day and one perfume another. This is especially true for prestige fragrances. The preference for a certain prestige fragrance develops as a consequence of acquired preference and remains a preference over a period of time (Swayne, Duncan, & Ginter, 2012). This is not to say that she will not be using any other perfume but her customer lifetime value will remain with Chanel. In this context, it is also imperative to note that marketing research revealed that the loyalty to a certain brand not only differs with the product category but also with gender.

Opportunities

The threat of new entry is low. This is so because the market is highly saturated. US women spend a lot on their grooming and personal care. They want to look their best and realize that it is important to set aside a certain proportion of their monthly budget for themselves. The brands that are currently there in the market are at their growth stage in the product life cycle. It is because of this reason that these brands keep coming up with variants or keep changing the packaging of the brands and their marketing communication messages

(Porter, 2008). They keep changing the brand ambassadors to revitalize the brands in the growth stage. However, it is also important to state that certain brands have been formed on the basis of such unique selling proposition that they are very difficult to compete. They cater to a different niche altogether.

PEST Analysis

The porter's five forces model is one of the most important models in marketing used for a comprehensive industry analysis. The model was given by marketing guru Michael E. Porter in the year 1979. This may be understood as a model which helps the marketers in assessing the balance of power in various business situations. The model is applicable to all form of business. A major advantage of this model is that it not only helps in the understanding of current position of a business but also helps in the crafting of a unique selling proposition in the future based on the assessment of current sources of power. Hence, the business is examined for both the strengths and weaknesses.

The five forces that have been selected for the model are used to identify two things on any given industry – the level of competition and the level of attractiveness of an industry. The level of competition and the level of attractiveness in an industry can change over time. These forces are micro in nature as they relate specifically to the chosen business entity. The five forces model is illustrated as under. This refers to the power that the suppliers of a company can exert upon it. This may take the form of increase in prices, payment terms, inventory turnover and others. The supplier power is the function of the number of alternatives available, the kind of supplies, and the cost of switching from one supplier to another (Porter, 1980). This relates to the ability of the buyers to bring prices down. This is a function of the kind of information that is there, the differentiation that exists in the products offered. The higher the switching cost the lower will be the buyer power.

Conclusion

Melaleuca cases to spotlight on creating products that help a healthy lifestyle and are more secure for the home. In the home, the organization concentrates on inquiring about and bringing to market cleaning products that utilization more common cleaning products that are guaranteed to be more secure than “brutal chemicals.” Melaleuca touts that its products are tantamount to or better than what is found at the neighborhood supermarket, however without the sanitizer, lye, or different chemicals ordinarily found in different brands. The organization has created a broad line of wholesome products, for example, vitamin and mineral supplements which claim to advance heart wellbeing, cardiovascular, and circulatory strain supplements, and a glucosamine product for healthy joints.

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